

PRACTICE OF HRIS IN SELECT PRIVATE HOSPITALS IN TAMILNADU

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Abstract:

The aim of this research paper is to find out the practices of Human Resources Information Systems (HRIS) in the select private hospitals of Tamil Nadu. For this study, the researcher has collected primary data through the structured questionnaire. Out of 216 private hospitals in Tamil Nadu, he has selected 30 HR managers working in 30 private hospitals, distributed structured questionnaires to them and used the five scales Likert technique to investigate opinion of the respondents. The study reveals that 33.3 % hospitals selected have used HRIS to the full extent; 43.4%, some extent and 23.3%, a limited extent. The results of the study are found through the survey that 80% hospitals have used HRIS for recruitment and selection; 74.3%, payroll and 40%, assessing and training the employees. This study has disclosed a gap between the expected application of HRIS and present level of use in the select private hospitals and also found the high cost, lack of infrastructure and knowledge and insufficient training to the employees as the main reasons that are responsible for not implementing HRIS successfully in the select private hospitals of Tamilnadu.

Key Words: HRIS, Private Hospitals, Recruitment and Selection, Training and Development & Payroll System

Introduction:

HRIS is a modern technique and is amazingly developed in the result of that, the world has become a global village. Recently; organisations have been performing human resource activities with the use of computer-based information systems. Hence, Human resource information system is an important element to run any organization. It becomes pivotal of the organisation. It is a part and parcel of Human Resource Management. It manages HR activities in all organisations in a more efficient way. It refers to the individual or staff or workforce within an organisation responsible for performing the tasks given to them for the achievement of goals and aim of the organisation, that is possible through proper recruitment and selection, proper orientation programme, training, skill developments, proper assessment of employees (performance appraisal). The main idea of HRIS is to allow for the HR function to become more efficient and to offer better information for decision-making. In addition, it gives right compensation and benefits, maintaining proper labour relations and ultimately offering safety, welfare and health concern of employees.

The human resource information system is not only related to other sectors but also with service organizations as hospitals. Over the last decade, private hospitals in Tamil Nadu have tremendously grown, which need a huge demand for skilled, knowledgeable, energetic and enthusiastic service providing personnel. But, such huge demand often does not match with inadequate supplies of such potential candidates.

In this context, HRIS is a computer-based application for assembling and processing data related to the human resources. It is worth mentioning that HRIS is not only limited to the computer hardware and software applications that comprise technical part of the system, but also includes the people, policies, procedures and data required to manage the HR functions.

Many authors have concluded that HRIS offers several benefits for both HR and working people. Overman (1992) has argued that the potential advantages of HRIS are faster information processing, greater information accuracy, improved planning and programme development, and enhanced employee communications. On the other side of the coin, while implementing HRIS in any organisation, most challenging and limiting constraint of HRIS is the high cost of conversion from manual based HRM to computer based HRM, inadequate training for HR people, lack of supportive infrastructure, as well as the shortage of technical know-how (Humayun Zafar-2012).

The main aim of this research paper is to explore the current scenario of HRIS in the various aspects of HRM and expectation of HR people related to the use of HRIS in the private hospitals of Tamil Nadu. Moreover, another aim of this paper is to find out the reasons behind the mismatch between the real and expected applications of HRIS in HRM.

Objectives of the Study:

The study has found out the applications of HRIS in private hospitals, Tamil Nadu. The specific objectives are given below.

- ✓ To look at the practice of HRIS in recruitment and selection, training and development and payroll system of the select private hospitals, Tamil Nadu.
- ✓ To discuss the perception of HR people in private hospitals of Tamil Nadu as to the application of HRIS in recruitment and selection, training and development and payroll system in detail.
- ✓ To find out the reason for the deviation from expected use and real use of HRIS in recruitment and selection, training and development and payroll system in private hospitals of Tamil Nadu.

Literature Review:

The past research studies conducted by various authors of different establishments of the practice of HRIS have been reviewed briefly below.

Ball, Kirstie S. (2001) has presented the results of a survey on the use of human resource information systems (HRIS) in smaller organisations. The survey has enquired as to the nature of information stored electronically in three core areas: personnel, training and recruitment as well as the type of information analysis being undertaken and also found significant relationships between the total number of people employed by the organisation and certain aspects of its information storage and manipulation. From the survey, it is understood that smaller organisations are less likely to use HRIS in their administration.

Sadri and Chatterjee (2003) have argued that Human Resource Information System plays an important role in the Human Resource Department of any organisation. It serves as a database for various HR functions like Human Resource Planning, Personnel Cost Planning, Training & Development, Performance Appraisal, etc. It is an integrated system, which is necessary to collect, record, store, manage, deliver and present data onto human resource. Hence, it promotes the effectiveness of human resource information system and shapes an interaction between human resource management and information technology. Further, this paper highlights the need, components, benefits and functions as HRIS in an organisation.

Syed Qudsiya Batool, Dr. M. A Sajid, & Dr. Syed Hassan Raza, (2012), has examined the use of HRIS, benefits and barriers in Accounts office and AJKCDP. The authors have constructed the questionnaires based on earlier studies. The result of their study has showed that the benefits of HRIS are quick response and easy access to information and

reducing manpower. But, lack of funds and trained staff is the greatest barriers in the use of HRIS in Accounts and AJKCDP.

Ms. Kamini Teotia Zenith (2012) has developed a human resource information system (HRIS) model, which consists of organisational vision, strategic integration, personnel development, communication and integration, records and compliance, knowledge management, HR analysis, and forecasting and planning. Finally, this research paper has concluded that the aim at HRIS is to merge the different parts of human resources, including payroll, labour productivity and benefit management into less capital-intensive system than the mainframe used to manage activities in the past.

Yasemin Bal Yıldız, Serdar Bozkurt & Esin Ertemsir Yıldız (2012) have argued that with the increasing effect of globalization and technology, organisations have started using information systems in various functions and departments in the last decades. This research paper has further presented that Human resources management is one of the departments that mostly use management information systems to find potential employees, to keep up complete records on existing employees, to create programs, to develop employees' talents' and skills, to help senior management, to show the manpower requirements, and to use HR systems for various HR practice such as workforce planning, staffing, compensation programs, salary forecasts, pay budgets and labour/employee relations. In this research, the authors have constructed questionnaires and distributed to HR employees to get access the effectiveness and use of HRIS in organisations. The result of the research further gives valuable insights about the success and effectiveness of HRIS in organisations.

Oyoo Mark Okinyi, Otieno K. Kelvin & Keatone K. Margaret (2013) has discussed that Human Resource Management has become one of the key resources of business organisations today. The need to integrate Human Resource Management (HRM) with information systems has become a necessity as modern firms are realizing that their people and information resources are vital for their survival. As a result, Human Resource Information Systems (HRIS) are now used extensively in all organisations irrespective of its size, tenure of establishment, complexities of operations etc. With the growing importance of human resource management and increasing the size of the organisations, maintenance of employee related data and generation of reports are the crucial aspects of any organisation. This paper has highlighted that more organisations are adopting computer-based human resource management systems (HRMS)

Barkha Gupta (2013) has said that an HRIS is basically an intersection of the human resources and information technology through an HR software solution. HRIS allows the HR activities and processes to occur electronically. The Human Resource Information System (HRIS) is a software solution to the data entry, data tracking, data information of the Human Resources, payroll, management, and accounting functions of a business. The goal of HRIS is to merge the different parts of the human resource, including payroll, labour productivity, and benefits management into a less capital-intensive system than the mainframes used to manage activities in the past. Generally, the HRIS should give the ability to more effectively plan, control and manage the HR costs; achieve improved efficiency and quality in the HR decision-making and make employee and managerial productivity and effectiveness. In most situations, an HRIS increases efficiency, when it comes to making decisions on HR. Lastly, this research paper helps to know how the HRIS helps the organisation enhance the efficiency of work.

Ama F. Karikari, Peter Agyekum Boateng, Evans O. N. D. & Ocansey (2015) has discussed that the evolution of technology has encouraged organisations to use human

resource information systems (HRIS), which contribute to the effectiveness of manpower activities in organisations. This research paper has interviewed two HR managers in the hospitality industry in the Greater Region (Ghana) to identify the benefits, contributions and the challenges of HRIS. It is revealed that HRIS has identified unfilled positions accurately, analysed each job position and its job title in the organisation, provided insight into organisational training needs, selected the right persons to be trained at the right time, evaluated the effectiveness of training programs and made faster and better decisions on successor ranking. This paper concludes that organisations should integrate HRIS with other organisational systems to facilitate speedy sharing with information and decision-making.

Methodology of the Study:

The study is conducted with an aim of inquiring into the application of HRIS in HRM, especially in service organisations like hospitals. Thus, the research is exploratory in nature.

a) Sample Selection: There are 216 private hospitals in Tamil Nadu, out of which 30 private hospitals have been selected on a random basis to investigate the role of HRIS in HRM.

b) Study Period and Data Collection Method: The study is conducted over a six month period from May 1st, 2016 to October 30th, 2016. Data for the study are collected through a structured questionnaire with the HR personnel of the select private hospitals in Tamil Nadu. Thus, the nature of the data is primary.

c) Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents: The researcher has interviewed 30 HR personnel working in 30 private hospitals, whose ages range from 30 to 58. Out of 30 respondents, 24 are male and the remaining 6, female. Among the HR personnel, 24 have sound knowledge in HR as they have specific training on HR, whereas the rest of the 6 have some HR related degree, but they do not have training in HR related activities.

d) Statistical Tools Used: The researcher has used the simple statistical tools like, frequency distribution, percentile, etc. to analyse collected data and highlighted the extent of use of the HRIS practiced, the perception of HR people about the importance of HRIS and the reason behind the gap between the real and expected practice of HRIS.

Results and Discussions:

1. HRIS Practice: HRIS is a systematic procedure for collecting, storing, maintaining, recovering data required by organisations about their human resources, personal activities and organisational characteristics (Kovach et al;2002) HRIS has different uses and benefits. It helps record and analyse the information related to the employees and organisations and in maintaining documents such as employee handbooks, emergency evacuation procedures, and safety procedure (Fletcher 2005 and Lee 2008). Many organisations have used HRIS not only for administrative purposes but also for strategic decision-making purposes. The following Table 1 presents responses of the respondents of this study with regard to the present status of HRIS practices in their hospitals of Tamil Nadu.

Table 1: Present Status of HRIS Practices in Private hospitals of Tamil Nadu

S.No	Particulars	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	Limited extent	10	33.3	33.3	---
2	Some extent	13	43.4	43.4	33.3
3	Full extent	7	23.3	23.3	76.7
	Total	30	100.0	100.0	100.0

Table 1 shows that only 7 private hospitals, which is only 23.3% out of 30 hospitals of Tamil Nadu surveyed, are practicing HRIS to full extent. Again, 13 private hospitals representing 43.4%, is practicing HRIS to some extent. The remaining 10 hospitals are practicing HRIS to a limited extent that is only (33.3%).

2. Recruitment and Selection, Training and Development and Payroll: Human Resource Management Processes includerecruitment and selection, training and development and payroll. Recruitment and selection arebuilding the block of any successful organization, belonging to value added HR Processes, managing high volumes of job resumes, having the ability to choose the right candidates and pushing them quickly through the organization. Further, in most of the organisations, training, and career development is very vital in any organization that aims at progressing and results with optimal utilization of resources in the organisation. Payroll is the process by which employers pay an employee for the work they have done.It creates a huge burden and unwanted stress for small business owners. To avoid these issues, small and middle-sized businesses can benefit from using payroll systems. In this survey, Table 2 presents the HR manager’s opinion with regard to the HRISpractice in recruitment and selection, training and development and payrollin select private hospitals of Tamil Nadu.

Table 2: HRIS Practices in Recruitment and Selection, Training and Development and Payroll

S.No	Description	Frequency		Percentage	
		No	Yes	No	Yes
1	Practice of HRIS in Recruitment and Selection	06	24	20.0	80.0
2	Practice of HRIS in Training and Development	18	17	60.0	40.0
3	Practice of HRIS in Payroll	08	22	26.7	73.3

Table 2 shows the extent of practicing HRIS in recruitment and selection, training and development and payroll in private hospitals of Tamil Nadu.Out of 30 selected for this study, 24 hospitals representing 80%; 22 hospitals, 73.3% and 17 hospitals, 40% practice HRIS in recruitment and selection; training and developmentandpayroll.

3. HR People’ Perception: According to Robbins (1996), perception can also be interpreted as a process by which individuals organize and interpret their sensory impressions to give meaning to their environment.The employees’ perception has a greater impact on the success of any organization. In this survey, Table 3 shows the HR person’s perception about the practice of HRIS inrecruitment and selection, training and development and payrollin the select private hospitals of Tamil Nadu

Table 3: HR People’ Perception about the Importance of HRIS

Description	Very Important		Important		No Comment		Not Much Important		Not Important at all	
	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%
Practice of HRIS in Recruitment and Selection	23	76.7	06	20.00	1	3.30	0	0	0	0
Practice of HRIS in Training and Development	16	53.3	12	40.00	2	6.67	0	0	0	0
Practice of HRIS in Payroll	20	66.67	07	23.33	3	10.00	0	0	0	0

The result of the study in Table 3 shows the HR person's perception about the HRIS importance in their private hospitals. Only 3.30%; 6.67% and 10% respondents did not make any comment about the HRIS importance in recruitment and selection; training and development and payroll system. 20%; 12% and 7% HR managers gave their opinions about the HRIS importance in recruitment and selection; training and development and payroll system separately. 76.70%; 53.3% and 66.67% of the respondents replied that HRIS was a very important tool for HRM-specific activities, namely recruitment and selection; training and development and payroll system.

4. The Deviation between Expected and Actual Application of HRIS: According to the views of the respondents, the following Table 4 highlights the reasons for gap behind the deviation between expected and real application of HRIS.

Table 4: Reasons behind the Deviation between Expected and Real Application of HRIS according to the view of the interviewees

S. No	Reasons	Frequency	Percentage
1	Costly	22	73
2	Time consuming	05	17
3	Lack of supportive Infrastructure	26	87
4	Lack of Expertise	20	67
5	Lack of Training for the HR People in HRIS	15	50

Table 4 shows high cost, time consumption, lack of supportive infrastructure, lack of expertise in HRIS and lack of training for the HR people in HRIS as reasons, which are behind the deviation between expected and real application of HRIS in the select private hospitals of Tamil Nadu. Of the five reasons shown in Table 4, 87% of the respondents have a unanimous opinion that the lack of supportive infrastructure is one of the main reasons in many private hospitals. 73% of the respondents have pointed out that a huge initial cost is considered as a second reason to create an obstacle to the introduction of HRIS in their hospitals. 67% and 50% of the respondents think that lack of expertise and lack of training for the HR people in HRIS are the third and fourth reasons. The 17% percentages of the respondents consider HRIS as a time-consuming tool, which has the least score among all the factors.

Conclusion:

The study has found out the significant role of Human Resources Information System in recruitment and selection, training and development and payroll administration in private hospitals of Tamil Nadu. It has identified the reasons for such a gap, namely; lack of supportive infrastructure development, high cost and insufficient training, between the expected and real application of HRIS in private hospitals of Tamil Nadu.

Suggestions:

- This research study has suggested that
- ✓ Every hospital, irrespective of size should set up HRIS in managing their human resource activities.
 - ✓ Every hospital should develop good infrastructure, which would enable them to recruit and select right people; give proper training to their workforce and offer better education with the desired reward for performances and
 - ✓ The initial cost for the introduction of HRIS in every hospital is highly expensive, but, in the long run, benefits that organisations receive will outweigh the initial costs.

References:

1. Over man, S. (1992). "Reaching for the 21st Century", HR Magazine, 37, pp.61 to 63.

2. Humayun Zafar. "Exploring Organizational Human Resource Information System Security" AMCIS 2012 Proceedings (2012). Available at: http://works.bepress.com/humayun_zafar
3. Ball, Kirstie S. (2001). "The use of human resource information systems: a Survey", *Personnel Review*, 30(6) pp.677to 693.
4. Sadri, J. and Chatterjee, V. (2003), "Building organizational character through HRIS", *International Journal of Human Resources Development and Management*, Vol. 3 No. 1, pp. 84-98.
5. Syeda Qudsia Batool, Dr. M.A Sajid, Dr. Syed Hassan Raza, (2012), "Benefits and Barriers of Human Resource Information System In Accounts Office &Azad Jammu &Kashmir Community Development Program," *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, Vol.1,No.3,pp.211to 217.
6. Ms. KainiTeotia Zenith (2012) "Role of HRIS in Performance Evaluation& Decision Making" *ZENITH International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research* Vol.2 Issue 4, April 2012, pp.229 to239.
7. Yasemin Bal Yıldız, Serdar Bozkurt and Esin Ertemsir Yıldız (2012,) "Importance Of Using Human Resources Information Systems (HRIS) And A Research On Determining The Success of HRIS" paper presented in international conference, 2012, pp.53 to 62.
8. Oyoo Mark Okinyi , Omieno K. Kelvin , Kitone K. Margaret (2013), "The Value Of Human Resource Information Systems In Human Resource Management," *Journal: International Journal of Computers & Technology*, Vol 11, No.10, pp.3086 to 3089.
9. Barkha Gupta (2013), "Human Resource Information System (HRIS): Important Element of Current Scenario" *IOSR Journal of Business and Management (IOSR-JBM)* e-ISSN: 2278-487X, p-ISSN: 2319-7668. Volume 13, Issue 6 (Sep. - Oct. 2013), pp. 41 to 46.
10. Ama F. Karikari, Peter Agyekum Boateng, Evans O. N. D. Ocansey (2015) "The Role of Human Resource Information System in the Process of Manpower Activities" *American Journal of Industrial and Business Management*, V. 5, pp.424 to 431.
11. Kovach, K.A., Hughes, A.A., Fagan, P., & Maggitti, P.G. (2002). "Administrative and strategic advantages of HRIS.*Employment Relations Today*", 29, 43-8.
12. Fletcher, P. (2005). "From personnel administration to Business Driven Human Capital Management: the Transformation of the Role of HR in the Digital age". In Greutal and Stone (Eds), *The Brave new World of her* (pp1-12). San Francisco, CA: Jossey-Bass.
13. Lee, A., (2008). "Relationship between the use of information technology and performances of human resource management". PhD thesis, Alliant International University, San Diego: USA.